

Diffusion of Si to fiber reinforced Al composites

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Summary

The composite used in this study is carbon-fiber reinforced aluminum prepared by laminating preformed sheets, each of which consists of opened carbon fibers coated with aluminum by the plasma spray method, and by subjecting them to a hot press. The specimens thus prepared underwent a heat treatment under vacuum and were subjected to examinations about the relationship between heating conditions and resultant strength and the influence of Si diffusion in the composite.

Experimental results are as follows. Si diffusion in carbon fiber reinforced aluminum is promoted by SiO_2 intervention, because the SiO_2 existing under vacuum makes reaction with Al easily. Si diffusion along interfaces in the composite goes through the following process:

also Si diffusion along the interfaces improves the high temperature characteristics.

Introduction

Fiber reinforced metals (FRM) are an up-to-date composite material attracting interests of the field of material research and development with its good characteristics, i.e. lightweight, high stiffness and higher heat resistance than fiber-reinforced polymers.(1) Among them, the carbon-fiber reinforced metals are one of the most attractive ones, because the carbon fibers therein will assure the products of excellent mechanical characteristics and low cost.

In order to put the carbon-fiber reinforced metals in practical application, however, many problems not only on the manufacturing and processing methods but also on the interface between fibers and the matrix must be solved, and that is why a variety of studies are still being made currently.(2)

The composite used in this study is carbon-fiber reinforced aluminum prepared by laminating preformed sheets, each of which consists or opened carbon fibers coated with aluminum by the plasma spray method, and by subjecting them to a hot press.(3) The specimens thus prepared underwent a heat treatment under vacuum and were subjected to examinations about the relationship between heating conditions and resultant strength and the influence of Si diffusion in the composite.(4)

Test Method

Specimens. The carbon fibers used in the tests are of Toho Besron's "Besfite" with the nominal fiber diameter of $7\mu\text{m}$. The fibers were delivered in a bundle consisting of 12,000 fibers and opened prior to use.

Characteristics of the fibers are given in Table 1. The opened fibers were wound on a drum of 15 cm wide and 70 cm in diameter, whereto a certain specified amount of aluminum powder was sprayed by the plasma spray method to produce preformed sheets. The composition of used aluminum powder is shown in Table 2.

Adjustment of the volume fraction (V_f) was made by controlling the rate of spraying. Specimens made of H.T. type fibers are equipped with a V_f of 30% while those of H.M. type with a V_f of approximately 10%.

In a press die, these preformed sheets thus made were placed in a stack of approximately 40 sheets and subjected to a hot press to obtain a plate of 6 cm \times 10 cm. The hot press conditions were such that a pre-pressure of 0.8 kg/mm² was applied for 10 min upon attaining a temperature of 560 °C to be followed by a pressure rise up to 6 kg/mm², at which the press was conducted. Each plate thus obtained was trimmed into a specimen of 1.8 cm \times 5 cm.

Heating. Upon locating in a uniform heated part of furnace, specimens were heated either under the low vacuum 10^{-1} torr and a higher one 10^{-4} torr. The heating was performed in two different arrangements in one of them, the specimen was contained in a boat placed in a furnace core pipe of opaque quartz, and in the other contained in a boat placed in a stainless-steel tubing in opaque quartz pipe. The intention thereof is to

allow in the former easy diffusion of Si from the quartz pipe by refraining from a double pipe construction and in the latter to allow only influence of heating to appear easily owing to incorporation of double pipe construction.(Fig.1) The two data were then examined comparatively.

For the purpose of comparison, specimens were prepared also by the ion-plating/hot press method in the same conditions.

Annealing was performed with the temperature range 300 °C to 650 °C and the duration 6 to 400 hr.

Structural Observation and Analysis Specimens after annealing were observed by optical microscope and SEM, and subjected to analysis for their C, Al and Si contents by EPMA and atomic extinction. The strengths of composites were measured by tensile tests.

Test Result and Discussion

Structural Observation Observation of the specimens by optical microscope and SEM has revealed that heating proceed recrystallization and grain growth of the aluminum matrix in both specimens prepared under the low and high vacuums.

Besides the above-mentioned phenomena, it has been as-certainated that the specimen exposed in a quartz pipe presentes Si precipitation along the boundary of those grown grains and the interface between carbon fibers and matrix.

The amount of Si precipitation can be seen more with longer time for treatment, and also more around the carbon fibers.

Typical structural changes of the specimens prepared by the plasma/hot press method and the ion-plating/vacuum hot press method are shown in Photos 1, 2, respectively, which inform that some parts present a structure similar to that of Al-Si alloy.

Radiographical, Atomic Extinctive and Auger Analyses As structural observations of the composites after heating have revealed that Si disperses during annealing, now the composites before treatment and after heating were subjected to an X-ray analysis, and the Si distribution therein was examined. Some models are given in Photo 3.

The quantitative analysis by the atomic extinction was performed and the result thereof is shown in Table 3.

In order to examine the influence of any adsorbed matters during manufacture of the composite, an analysis was made by the Auger electronic spectrum method. Analysis of the Auger spectrum obtained was made by reference to the standard spectrum, and the quantitative analysis is used the relative sensitivity factors. Auger peaks used in this quantitative analysis were C(273 eV), O(503 eV), Al(1396 eV) and Si(1622 eV).

Photo1 Optical micrograph of specimens fabricated by hot press method in air

Photo2 Optical micrograph of specimens fabricated by hot press method in vacuum

A. S.E.M.

B. Al

C. C

D. Si

Photo 3 Electron probe microanalyses of composites

A : Vacuum pump D : Bout and sample
 B : Thermo couple E : Stainless pipe
 C : Furnace

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of experimental apparatus

The quantitative analysis will entail error to some degree, as the primary electron beam was assumed to be at 10 kV. This quantitative analysis was performed on the assumption that the specimens were composed only of Al, C, O and Si, and they were calculated in terms of atom densities. An example of Auger spectrum is shown in Fig.2.

A comparison of specimens without experience of heating treatment with those heated for a long time indicates clearly that O exists at every interface and in every matrix, while Si is found only in the heated specimens.

Seen as a whole, Al in the specimens heated at 600°C for 95 hr takes the initial state of oxidation, and it is likely that the C in the neighborhood of interfaces has formed some compound (SiC or Al₄C₃). The values obtained by this quantitative analysis are given in Table 4, but it is not recommended to use these values for evaluation of the whole composite, because, besides the above-mentioned error, this measuring process involves some weak point such that the time for sputtering is too short and that the Auger analysis consists of a spot analysis on the surface of the specimen.

Influence of Long-Time Heating to Strength Figure 3 shows the result of treatment at 600°C under both vacuum conditions, 10⁻¹ torr and 10⁻⁴ torr.

In the case of low vacuum σ/σ_0 drops with increasing time for heating, but in the case of high vacuum the strength drops by approximately 20% in the first six hours, whereafter stays at a constant level regardless of the heating time.

This drop of strength during low vacuum treatment may be due to high oxygen content, as evident on the data of Auger analysis, and also to damages caused by the adsorbed air at the surface of carbon fibers.

Drop of the strength in the initial period of high vacuum treatment, on the other hand, may be due to deterioration resulting from the adsorbed oxygen, and its being held constant thereafter will be due to Si diffusion at the interfaces which serves for prevent the chemical reaction between aluminum and fibers, and also to improved adhesives.

Diffusion Mechanism of Si It is revealed by the microscopic, radiographic, atom extinctive and Auger analyses, that specimens with treatment directly exposed to vacuum contain Si while the specimens with treatment enclosed in a stainless-steel tubing do not contain any Si. Thus it is necessary now to disclose the diffusion mechanism of Si. As described above, the aluminum powder for metal spraying contains a minimum amount of Si, so that it can be properly considered that the furnace core pipe (quartz pipe) itself is reduced according to the following equation and then diffused.

Reaction between SiO₂ and Al takes place reportedly in such a procedure that a reaction according to the above equation occurs at a

Fig. 2 Auger electron spectra of A-106
 a: Matrix
 b: Interface

Fig. 3 Relation between annealing time and σ/σ_0 .

temperature exceeding 400°C in a glass-fiber reinforced aluminum and, over 500°C in particular, much reaction arises to cause worsened characteristics to the composite itself.(5) In this glass-fiber reinforced aluminum, the two elements have direct contact with each other, but this reaction can arise in the carbon-fiber reinforced aluminum concerned herein without direct contact to lead to diffusion of Si into the composite.

According to this mechanism of Si diffusion, aluminum as component of the composite evaporates at the surface and is evaporated fast to the inner wall of quartz pipe to reduce SiO₂, and thus SiO is produced. This gaseous SiO is reduced by the aluminum in the composite and has diffused into the composite. This reaction takes place according to the following equations:

It is revealed that the Si diffusion is also uni-directional. For example, there is a clear difference between the thickness direction and the fibers' axial direction. This directionality will be discussed now.

This composite is fabricated by not hot press. Here the interface between fibers and matrix does not consist of chemical bond but of mechanical adhesion. Therefore it should be considered that the bond is formed by difference of the thermal expansion coefficients between carbon fibers and aluminum. At a high temperature, accordingly, expansion of the aluminum brings about looseness to the interfaces between this and the carbon fibers, and along these loose interfaces Si diffuse to cause high Si density around the carbon fibers, to be followed by further diffusion in the course of time along the interfaces of recrystallized matrix and even inside the crystals.

Si contain in this case will further promote Si diffusion, because eutectic crystals of Al and Si are formed in this part, partially in liquid phase. Now the effect of Si diffusion will be discussed: Even though interfaces in this composite consist of a physical adhesion, some parts may be of chemical bond, which can cause formation of Al₄C₃. It is known that such an interface compound gives rise to deterioration in the carbon fibers.(6) The result of this study says, however, that Si diffuses along the interfaces to suppress formation of Al₄C₃, which is the weakest inter-phase compound. In other words, Si diffusion has favorable affection upon the high-temperature stability of this type of composite.

Conclusion

Conclusions are summarized as follows:

- 1) Si diffusion in carbon-fiber reinforced aluminum is promoted by SiO₂ intervention, because the SiO₂ existing under vacuum makes reaction with Al easily.
- 2) Si diffusion along interfaces in the composite goes through the following process:

$$3\text{SiO}_2 + 2\text{Al} \rightarrow 3\text{SiO} + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$$

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- 3) Si diffusion along the interfaces improves the high temperature characteristics

References

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Table 1 Propeties of carbon fiber

	H T Type	H M Type
Youngs modulus(kg/mm ²)	24200	35000
Fracture stress (kg/mm ²)	330	250
Fracture strain	0.0138	0.0072
Density (g/cm ³)	1.76	1.96

Table 2 Chmical composition of Aluminium powder (plasmalloy 100-D) for plasma spray, mesh 325 (weight%)

Si	Mg	Cu	Fe
0.062	<0.01	<0.01	0.11

Table 3 Analytical results

Sample	Si (%)
Al Powder	0.0632
H.T. Carbon fiber	0.0481
A-106	10.2
A-303	1.34

Table4 Analytical results

Sample	Place	Al (%)	C (%)	O (%)	Si (%)
A-100	Matrix	90.5	5.3	3.8	0.39
	Interface	64.8	29.7	5.2	0.33
A-106	Matrix	55.1	11.2	17.3	16.4
	Interface	39.9	26.1	20.3	13.6

